

ATTITUDE TO MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENT

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Abstract. Most of the study of attitudes towards mathematics involved older children and adults. Checking the early development of attitudes towards mathematics is of particular importance in order to understand the relationship between them and real indicators and, if possible, to prevent the development of a strong negative attitude.

Key words: Intelligence, development, intuition, perception, attitude.

ОТНОШЕНИЕ К МАТЕМАТИКЕ У МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНИКА

Аннотация. В исследовании отношения к математике большую часть времени занимались дети старшего возраста и взрослые. Проверка раннего развития отношений к математике имеет особое значение для понимания связи между ними и реальными показателями и, по возможности, предотвращения развития резкого отрицательного отношения.

Ключевые слова: Интеллект, развитие, интуиция, восприятие, мироощущение.

Mathematics is necessary for children to have the knowledge and skills necessary for their daily lives, teaching them how to solve a problem, acquiring ways of thinking and preparing them for the future. The prejudices that arise in relation to mathematics affect the imagination of students regarding this course. Students' low enthusiasm for mathematics and high anxiety are one of the most important problems. This study was conducted with third and fourth graders of elementary schools in the Istanbul region to check their mathematical motivation and concerns. He came to the conclusion that students' motivation for mathematics is at a medium level, and mathematics concerns are very low, there is no difference in gender. The mathematics motivation of fourth graders was higher than that of third graders.

Classroom teachers can be advised to prepare an environment in which students can introduce an interesting world of mathematics. Mathematics depends not only on cognitive abilities, but also on emotional factors and attitudes. Several studies have shown that emotional factors can play a major role in mathematical performance, with mathematics anxiety playing a particularly large role. One possible reason for the negative link between mathematical anxiety and real performance is that people with high levels of mathematical anxiety are more likely to avoid activities and situations that involve mathematics, and therefore have less practice. Mathematical anxiety can also directly affect performance by overloading working memory.

For example, people who are very concerned about mathematics have much lower working memory capacity than people with lower levels of mathematical anxiety when performing math-related tasks. The relationship between mathematical anxiety and performance can also be in a different direction. Low mathematical ability can lead to math anxiety as a result of repeated failure experiments. Indeed, anxiety and performance can be a vicious circle that negatively affects each other. The development of math anxiety can also be associated with social factors, such as exposure to teachers who themselves suffer from math anxiety, as well as pre-existing difficulties in digital cognition. Initial mathematical difficulties

can also be more vulnerable to negative social influences. Most of the study of attitudes towards mathematics involved older children and adults.

Checking the early development of attitudes towards mathematics is of particular importance in order to understand the relationship between them and real indicators and, if possible, to prevent the development of a strong negative attitude. A relatively small number of studies that have studied the attitude of younger children to mathematics have generally shown a positive attitude, with most children claiming to love mathematics. However, studies show that relationships can get worse with age, especially during high school, but also in the primary age group. This showed an increased concern for mathematics, as well as an increased interest in mathematics during the later primary school years. Many studies carried out between high school students and adults are consistent in showing real performance in mathematics, with a positive and negative association with mathematical anxiety, with the liking of mathematics and a high self-esteem in mathematics. This is the case not only for advanced mathematics, but also for basic magnitude comparison skills.

The study of the relationship between attitudes and performance in mathematics in younger children did not lead to the same accurate results as in older children. Thus, the relationship between relationship and performance can be more pronounced in the following initial years. This study is aimed at studying the relationship between success in mathematics, math anxiety, unhappiness from poor performance, liking mathematics, and self-assessment in elementary (grade 3; Age 7-8) and later primary (grade 5) children. From 9 to 10 years old). Based on previous studies that have used a similar method, the mathematics will be related to the liking of mathematics and self-assessment of the ability in the subject, but not to anxiety. In addition, especially, although mathematics anxiety is a major area of research, not all attitudes towards mathematics are negative and some people express a strong liking for mathematics.

This seems to be especially true of mathematically gifted people, but is not limited to them. Another objective was to study the changes between the 3rd grade and the 5th grade. It has been suggested that older children may have a more negative attitude. We also aimed to consider that the relationships between different variables can vary between Class 3 and Class 5. Although any such analysis should be approximate due to the reduction in numbers, the relationship between the effectiveness of mathematics and other relationship variables was predictable. and it may not be particularly noticeable in the 3rd grade between indicators in mathematics and self-assessment, but it may be significant in the 5th grade. Mathematics focuses on the consideration of gender differences in efficiency and relationships. Many current studies show that women do not work lower in mathematics than men, but they value themselves lower and worry more. The study aims to check whether such gender differences are already present in young children.

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